

TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: At present, attention to the non-development of the economy, in particular tourism, is growing all over the world, as well as in Uzbekistan. People spend their free time effectively, trying to relax, restore their health, to know the world, the customs, values of peoples. Such services are provided by the tourism industry. Humanity has always sought to change the circle of its movement, to discover new lands. In this article, opinions and comments will be made about the current program and plans for the development and development of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: tourism industry, development, beaches, tourist tour projects, Culture, visiting tourism.

Uzbekistan entered the new XXI century with the steps continuously. It is predicted that the 21st century will be the age of Tourism and tourism. In the 21st century, tourism provides foreign exchange earnings in the budget of the Republic with its significant contribution. All-round opportunities and grounds are sufficient for this in our republic. Only by implementing the strategy of modern tourism development should we create the opportunity to raise the tourism sector to the top.

If we pay attention to statistics, the visit of foreign tourists to our country grew by 32 percent in 2017 and by 100 percent in 2018. But there is another aspect of the matter. The regulatory documents regulating the tourism sector were not yet perfect, and the lack of hotels and the necessary infrastructure did not allow the rapid development of this direction.

The decision of the head of our state “on measures for the rapid development of the tourism network” finds a solution to the problems. "Tourism contributes to employment activities in these regions, attracts the people who are not employed in public production, the application of labor sector widen. Cooperation in the field of tourism will contribute to the development of the economy, the effective use of regional resources and the professional development of the employees of the service sector. The tourist network will help to accelerate the development of agricultural production and improve it. In the future, the number of people employed in the service sector will increase with the decrease in the provision of services to the population. The rapid development of the network through cooperation in the field of tourism, the growth of its economic importance has led to the fact that the tourist service sector can bring great benefits, a lot of investment in this area is spent. Despite the fact that it requires a lot of money, the investment in the tourist industry is very profitable, because it covers itself relatively quickly. Receipts from foreign tourists turn into income and are in circulation in various branches of the national economy.

Currently, the process of forming a national model of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan is being carried out. In this model, it is noted that the tourist market developed in the country, like any other market, affects the socio – political and economic situation of the country. It is an important tool in the development of cooperation between the countries and in determining the levels of investment and capital flow. It is known that in developed countries of the market economy, mainly private and commercial companies serve tourists. However, under any circumstances, tourism can develop only if the state is destined to create the optimal economic and legal ground. If the state does not deal with the issues of Professional Training, protection of natural and cultural environment, information and advertising work and simplification of formality etc., then tourism will not be able to achieve the level of development as expected.

The sustainable development of the economy of the regions is often determined by the development of the social sphere and the tourism network. Accordingly, at present, tourism as a leading network of national economies has its significant share in the sustainable development of certain countries. The tourism sector is becoming an important factor in the development of human potential. Therefore, this is reflected in the creation of new jobs in a particular country or territory, the attraction of additional investments, the increase in tax revenues, the preservation of cultural, historical and natural resources, as well as rational use.

In the message of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis "we will continue consistent reforms in the development of Tourism in 2021. A particular attention is paid to the development of pilgrimage tourism and domestic tourism in particular. It has also been identified as an important direction to note that" 1 trillion sums will be allocated from the budget for the improvement of land, water and road infrastructure around tourism facilities". This necessitates the development of proposals and recommendations of the directions of its development, having studied the scientific-methodological and practical aspects of the structural elements and functions of the territorial tourism infrastructure.

In summary, public organizations at the national level: the Association of social tourism was established in order to cover all categories of tourists and create suitable conditions for them. This association contributes to the development of tourism in Uzbekistan unification of individuals wishing to contribute and their efforts to the development of social tourism orientation, including the organization of trips of children, youth, elderly, as well as citizens with disabilities. At the same time, cooperation with foreign associations on the development of inclusive tourism establishes relations.

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